

What is the Civic Data Cooperative?

CDC Workshop, 11th May 2021

Presented by Gary Leeming, LCR Civic Data Cooperative

Imagine...

A new type of civic platform that...

- Supports citizens in the decisions about them, with them
- Builds on existing success and partnerships to constantly improve care and services - LHP, CIPHA, C&M ICS, KQ, Innovation Agency, Growth Hub, LCR-CA
- Understands how to use data and research within every aspect of our work with transparency and public support

Creating a one-of-a-kind platform

Create a vibrant data environment

1. Because it creates the **positive changes citizens want** and the **economic growth the region needs**
2. By providing the **behavioural infrastructure** for people to choose to work with a **common purpose** to make **innovation easier**
3. Within a new **open, transparent, trusted environment**
4. That makes citizens' **health-related data work for the people** while preserving their **privacy** and respecting their preferences

What must be true?

To create the shared commitment needed for change

- We have a social license to act
- Clearly identified benefits and outcomes
- The perceived benefits for participating outweigh the risks
- There is an urgency to creating the vision
- We can build and sustain trust and collaboration
- Insight must be generated from lived experience / ground truth
- The impact of innovation must be measurable
- There needs to be clearly defined rules for ethical and inclusive use of data as a commons resource

What must be true?

To create the shared commitment needed for change

- We have a social license to act
- Clearly identified benefits and outcomes
- The perceived benefits for participating outweigh the risks
- There is an urgency to creating the vision
- We can build and sustain trust and collaboration
- Insight must be generated from lived experience / ground truth
- The impact of innovation must be measurable
- There needs to be clearly defined rules for ethical and inclusive use of data as a commons resource

That we have your help and know-how to create strategic plan and vision

Project Delivery

Agreed success criteria

1. Create an operational CDC
2. Creation of co-development framework
3. Industry and SME Partnerships w/ NHS and research
4. Economic Growth
5. Sustainability

Existing and potential projects

Being delivered or in delivery

Research Projects:

- CIPHA Expansion
- C-GULL
- BRC
- Imaging Databank
- Anti-microbial Resistance
- Event Research Programme

Community Projects:

- Design for Impact
- Age Well data linkage
- Citizen Jury
- Synthetic data / Sandbox
- Company advice / consultancy
- Safer Water Partnership?

Trust: Design Principles

The guardrails for design and decision making

Community

We believe that collaboration creates a bigger benefit than competition and that data is a common resource whose use should be defined by those who the data are about as well as those who collect the data.

Learning

We believe that learning is a continuous process, that we should always be challenged to improve through listening, and that we should share our knowledge and enthusiasm with others.

Open

We believe that to be truly accountable we should be open and transparent about our activities, about how data are used, and how choices are made.

Simplify

We believe we should always seek to simplify our work to make it easier to communicate and understand, to help others get the best care and get their jobs done.

Impactful

We believe that to be impactful we need to measure what we do, to make benefits tangible, and build for the future.

Protect

We believe it is important to define the boundaries of responsibility, to demonstrate trustworthy behaviours and be clear about our expectations for partners and collaborators.

Supporting Project Design

- Evaluating projects against design principles
- Designing projects to meet requirements

Impact		
We are unable to evidence the benefits of implementing the project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We are able to evidence the benefits of implementing the project.
We are unsure how to measure and monitor our project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have a set of measure that will allow us to measure and monitor our work throughout the duration of the project.
We are unsure what methods we can use to collect information for our project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We are able to use different methods to collect information for our project.
Open		
We don't have a process to publicise project information with the public	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have a clear process that publicises project information with the public
Our project activities and outputs will not be made freely available.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	Our project activities and outputs will be made freely available
Collaboration		
We don't know how to set up a collaborative working agreement between all project partners.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have an agreement in place between all project partners that fosters collaborative working.
We don't understand the factors that may influence the achievement or non-achievement of the project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We understand the factors that may influence the achievement or non-achievement of the project.
We don't understand how to create a shared purpose in our project	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We understand that we have become part of a project with a shared purpose
Simplify		
We are unsure how to make sure our communication is accessible to our stakeholders and public.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have a plan to ensure that the way we communicate with our stakeholders and the public is accessible.
Our project does not contribute towards enhancing access to/quality of care	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	Our project will contribute towards enhancing access to/quality of care
Our project does not contribute towards enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in the health system	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	Our project will contribute towards enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in the health system
Learning		
We don't have a process for capturing thoughts and opinions from people in our project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have created a process that allows us to capture thoughts and opinions from people in our project.
We don't know how to include people with lived experiences within our project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have project activities that allow those with lived experiences to share their knowledge.
We don't know how to implement learning and recommendations in our project to increase the effectiveness of project delivery.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We know how to implement learning and recommendations in our project to increase the effectiveness of project delivery.
Protect		
We are unsure how to protect patient and public data in our project.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	We have a plan to ensure that public and patient data is protected in our project.

Target Operating Model

Two key components

Outer Cycle	Technical Infrastructure	Data ecosystem	Shared Code	Trustworthy Digital Research	Sandbox
Inner Cycle	People Infrastructure	Inclusive Design	Public Involvement	Partnerships	Policy and Research

Key Previous Workshop Outputs

Winning hearts and minds across the whole system is essential.

Only by doing so will:

- people be willing to share data, and
- stakeholders have the motivation to actively engage with the CDC.

This will require (non-exhaustive list):

- listening, to understand ground truths across the whole system;
- transparency;
- a clear purpose that resonates across the whole system;
- deliberately building trust across the whole system;
- demonstrating public desire for involvement by presenting evidence from a non-biased group of people
- a clear and meaningful narrative for partnership involvement;
- evidence that the approach is desirable, feasible and viable, initially via case studies.

It is vital to focus on doing 100% of one thing well and avoid mission creep.

The near-term focus should be on producing a case study to demonstrate desire, build momentum and deliver impact.

Activities

Outputs

Outcomes

Intermediate outcomes

Long-term outcomes

Impact

Trust earned through CDC collaborations to build:

Accountability structure

Real world digital design eco-system

Policy and Research

Enabling partnerships and collaborations

SME & Industry collaboration

Patient and Public involvement

Impactful, Open, Collaboration, Simplify, Learning, Protect

Shared value cycle

Health and care organisations can understand real world challenges through integration of data and insight

Novel research ideas are developed within LCR to improve health and well being

Infrastructure for learning and testing 'Real World' solutions to problems

Trust is built with the public through a collaborative approach to ensure learning, understanding and boundaries of how civic data are used

Develop tools and expertise to establish resilient systems to respond to public health challenges and emergencies

Ensure the health system is fully fit for the future population health and public health

Open innovation testbed established to help attract investment to LCR and the UK that will make people's lives better

Direct ways for patients and services users to translate lived experience to insight are created

Culture of collaboration and open innovation to support realisation of shared value for health and care

UK leadership in building civic data environments enhanced through the region's reputation for making impactful change

Digital health collaborative partnerships and investments reduce the costs and risks for SMEs and industry to develop products and services

Citizens feel empowered to use their data to create positive change

Reduction in health inequalities to support better health and well-being to support the achievement of the UN SDG

Activities

Outputs

Outcomes

Intermediate outcomes

Long-term outcomes

Impact

Trust earned through CDC collaborations to build:

Accountability structure

Real world digital design eco-system

Policy and Research

Enabling partnerships and collaborations

SME & Industry collaboration

Patient and Public involvement

Impactful, Open, Collaboration, Simplify, Learning, Protect

Shared value cycle

Health and care organisations can understand real world challenges through integration of data and insight

Novel research ideas are developed within LCR to improve health and well being

Infrastructure for learning and testing 'Real World' solutions to problems

Trust is built with the public through a collaborative approach to ensure learning, understanding and boundaries of how civic data are used

Develop tools and expertise to establish resilient systems to respond to public health challenges and emergencies

Ensure the health system is fully fit for the future population health and public health

Open innovation testbed established to help attract investment to LCR and the UK that will make people's lives better

Direct ways for patients and services users to translate lived experience to insight are created

Culture of collaboration and open innovation to support realisation of shared value for health and care

UK leadership in building civic data environments enhanced through the region's reputation for making impactful change

Digital health collaborative partnerships and investments reduce the costs and risks for SMEs and industry to develop products and services

Citizens feel empowered to use their data to create positive change

Reduction in health inequalities to support better health and well-being to support the achievement of the UN SDG

How might we develop tools and expertise to establish resilient systems to respond to public health challenges and emergencies?

Successful if?

- **Information governance is clearly understood with rapid processes for sharing data within the law while enabling novel responses to public health challenges**
- **Have tested a toolkit for multi-disciplinary learning health system approach with delivery of project**

How might we ensure learning health system is fit for future health and public health needs?

Successful if?

- **Multi-disciplinary / multi-organisation teams are normal, with different skills and resources available to projects as needed**
- **Researchers have trusted access to routinely collected data within Liverpool that is linked across health and civic sources to identify and answer population health questions**

How might we enable private sector partners access an open innovation testbed that will make people's lives better

Successful if?

- **Digital diagnostics companies are able to access data to test and evaluate products to generate evidence that meets NICE guidelines**
- **CDC has a working sandbox that can test ideas using synthetic data that can then be tested using "blackbox" on real data**

How might we support patients and service users to create and access tools to translate lived experience to insight used to improve care and wellbeing

Successful if?

- **Citizens are able to access information about how their record is being used and contribute additional information to support researchers and system change**
- **Public engagement, such as citizen juries, is regularly used to test ideas for use of data**

Summary

Key themes for delivery

- With the support of our citizens, the CDC will follow its design principles to create an open, learning platform for partnerships across the NHS and care
- Create toolkits and case studies through projects that inspire and encourage new ideas to improve health and well-being across the region.
- Develop links with citizens, communities, civic and health partners, and commercial organisations who want to help co-create and build new solutions for health and care

Why your perspectives are valuable

We can't do it alone

- Need your know-how and intelligence
- Creating a rich picture of shared value CDC needs to create
- Based on collaboration
- Understanding future opportunities

Purpose of workshop

- Create unified vision of CDC strategic objectives
- Identify opportunities for the CDC
- Inform prioritisation of CDC next actions

Thanks for listening

Mural link:

<https://bit.ly/CDC-workshop-21>

Project Delivery

Plans for the next five years

- Year 1: DIAGNOSE AND DISCOVER. Build networks and soft infrastructure; Engage with local communities and organisations; Develop links with SME and industry communities, test project ideas
- Years 2 & 3: TREATMENT AND DELIVERY. Identify and manage research and development projects to improve health and care; develop infrastructure and digital commons
- Year 4+: SUSTAIN AND REUSE Sustainability, project completion, evaluation.

Wrapping Up and next actions

- Write up and share outputs
- Develop initial Design for Impact process and work with ICS partners to identify ideas and collaborators
- Establish formal steering group